

You are lost!

You are not sure how you arrived here, your memory of the last few days is hazy at best, but with others from the light you must return.

There are no others around to direct you, it is a time where phones and other connected technology do not work, maybe they never worked.

This is a time of knights, goddesses, dragons and relics. You need to journey back, but your energy is low and you have supplies for a few days at most.

You must explore the routes home and select one for your journey. Choose thoughtfully; not doing so could be your end!

Gameplay

GMless worldbuilding

Tone

Fantasy + Exploration

Players

3-6

Materials

- Six pebbles
- A six-sided die
- Six cards
- Map
- Paper for notes and drawings
- Writing utensils

Time

20 minutes per path

Ideals...

Envision: When asked to envision, imagine a place, artifact, or scene in the landscape.

Work with others: When envisioning with other players, discuss and work together. Current player can have final word.

Sound: landscapes are not silent, rather a hive of noise, music and other sounds. Work with this notion.

Setup

1. Each player should choose a pebble, depending on the number of players this could be more than one.
2. Set up the sound generator and speakers, making sure to turn on and connect the pebbles.
3. Place the map in the centre of the play area, being careful as it is old and might crumble to the touch. You can of course choose to draw your own map, imagining a place long forgotten, a time of inns on the roads to and in-between forests and cliffs, with the sea smashing against and rolling into caves used by smugglers.

Mythology: This is not a story of science, rather one of magic, strange slips in time, and other imaginings, that can be prioritized over science.

History: Each path may have a variety of elements, but try and induce a general feeling of the place that captures the essence of the world history and its mysteries.

4. As a group envision your band of lost souls:
 - Where are you from?
 - What is your shared outlook?
 - How did you come to get here?
5. Each player envisions their lost soul
 - Are you human, dwarf, robot, or another thing?
 - What does your backpack contain?
 - How do you miss home?
 - What drew you away to this place?
6. Roll a die to choose one or more artifacts to place on the map.

1. Crown	2. Treasure
3. Hazel	4. Dagger
5. Book	6. Magic potion
7. When everyone is ready, begin discovering a route home.

Explore a route

1. Choose someone to go first. This player should pick up the die, while other players should take hold of their pebble.
2. Beginning with the chosen player, roll a die to choose one of the six cards, then explore where on the map it might be.
3. Choose one or two players to interact with a pebble and listen to the sounds to set the mood of the location.
4. Roll the die to learn how your journey interacts with this element:

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|--------------|--|
| 1. Gentle | It emits the light. |
| 2. Fog | A deadly fog rises and kills you. |
| 3. Smugglers | A hideout for dangerous smugglers. |
| 4. Windy | A wild wind rises, roll both die:
- less than 8 and you are blown away
- greater than 8 and it passes you by |
| 5. Willow | Find willow twigs to make a crown and roll a die, greater than 2 and you must dance, otherwise put on the crown. |
| 6. Horses | A group pass riding at pace, you hide in the dark. |

5. Imagine this place and the interaction, allow the sound to change your perception and feeling. Note down a short passage, maybe along with a drawing. What sounds might you make and or expect here?
6. Pass the die to the next player. Rotation does not matter. That player then interacts with an element. Continue this loop until all element cards have been chosen.

Scrapbook

1. The group comes up with a name for the route. Record it on the map and in your scrapbook.
2. As a group discuss the mysteries of the route:
 - Is this the route that will lead to a safe journey home, is the dark kept at bay?
3. When you want to finish the game or all cards have been completed, then pick the route that will likely get you home to the light.

Pick a route

1. Each player picks a route for the journey home.
2. Discuss and consider the consequences of the different choices, and at some point the game comes to an end.
3. Fullstop!

pebble

